

**EFFICACY OF SIDDHA FORMULATION CHUKKU THAILAM
NASIYAM IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC SINUSITIS (PEENISAM)
– A CASE SERIES**

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Nasiyam is a traditional Siddha therapy involving the administration of oils or herbal extracts into the nasal passages to address disorders related to the head, particularly those associated with kabam (phlegm) imbalance. **Objective:** This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Nasiyam therapy, specifically using Chukku Thailam for 3 days, in treating Chronic sinusitis and related upper respiratory conditions in patients attending the Nanju Maruthuvam department OPD. **Methodology:** A case series of patients presenting with symptoms such as sneezing, rhinitis, nasal congestion, headache, and heaviness of head were treated with Nasiyam therapy using Chukku Thailam for three consecutive days. The Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT) was used to assess the severity of symptoms pre- and post-treatment. Demographic data and medical histories were collected, adverse events were monitored along with further follow-up for 2 months. **Results:** The results indicated a significant reduction in symptoms across most patients. Pre-treatment assessments showed higher symptom severity scores, which decreased after three days of Nasiyam therapy. The majority of patients reported relief from symptoms with no recurrence of symptoms was observed, suggesting a lasting therapeutic effect. Patients also expressed high satisfaction with the treatment, noting improvements in their quality of life. **Conclusion:** The treatment reduced sinusitis with significant reduction in SNOT scores across all 15 participants. 4 participants experienced substantial improvement, with near-complete symptom relief, while other cases showed moderate symptom reduction. This study supports the effectiveness of Nasiyam as a therapeutic intervention for managing chronic sinusitis. Future clinical studies, including randomized controlled trials, are necessary to confirm its efficacy, safety, and long-term benefits, and to explore its role in integrative medical practices.

Keywords: Nasiyam therapy, Chukku Thailam, sinusitis, chronic rhinitis, Sino-Nasal Outcome Test, Siddha medicine, nasal drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION:

Nasiyam is a targeted therapeutic procedure for addressing disorders of the head [1]. In this practice, medicinal formulations, including oils or herbal extracts, are administered directly into the nasal passage. Traditional Siddha literature describes Nasiyam as an effective way to correct imbalances in kabam (phlegm) and treat kabam-related ailments. The Therayar poem “**Pini anuga vidhi**” states, performing Nasiyam once every 45 days for maintenance, though the frequency may vary based on the severity of specific conditions [2]. As a primary method to restore balance in the thirithodam (three humors: vatham, pitham, and kabam), Nasiyam is commonly used for head and neck issues, as these regions are closely linked to kabam [3]. It is beneficial in alleviating conditions such as cold, cough, rhinitis, headache, chest congestion from chronic bronchitis, nasal disorders, and neuro-musculoskeletal issues like cervical spondylitis, facial paralysis, hemiplegia, frozen shoulder, mental health concerns, Parkinson’s disease, and even certain skin problems. Nasiyam is also useful in emergencies, such as for patients with unconsciousness caused by imbalance in humor or cases of poisoning and even snake bite. Besides aiding in disease prevention, Nasiyam supports the health of the sensory organs, preventing premature greying of hair, reducing hair fall, and promoting hair growth [2].

This approach utilizes the nasal cavity’s large surface area, high blood flow, and ability to bypass first-pass metabolism, allowing for rapid absorption into the bloodstream. After administration, drugs may be absorbed through several mechanisms: transcellular (across cells), paracellular (between cells), or through active processes like carrier-mediated transport. Small

particles pass easily through the mucus layer, while larger particles may struggle, as the mucus (containing mucin) can bind compounds and impact their movement. Absorption speed and efficiency depend on the drug's molecular weight and lipophilicity; water-soluble drugs with high molecular weights (>1000 Daltons) may have lower bioavailability, while lipid-soluble drugs absorb faster. Obstacles include drug clearance by the nasal mucociliary system (a protective mechanism moving mucus to the throat) and potential degradation before reaching circulation. Once drugs cross the nasal epithelium, they can follow different pathways to the brain. In the neurological pathway, drugs move slowly along olfactory neurons to the olfactory bulb. Alternatively, drugs may travel rapidly through the perineural space (paracellular transport) or enter the bloodstream via the vascular pathway, later crossing the blood-brain barrier (BBB) to reach the brain [4,5,6].

Sinusitis is correlated with Peenisam in Siddha system of medicine by standard terminologies in siddha published by World Health Organization [7]. The symptoms of peenisam includes, sneezing, rhinitis, itching of nose, cold, cough etc [8, 9]. This study involves the evaluation of effectiveness of nasiyam therapy in the treatment of sinusitis for the patients attending the Nanju Maruthuvam department.

FIGURE – 1 POSSIBLE MECHANISM OF NASIYAM

METHODOLOGY:

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE FOR NASIYAM:

The patient is instructed to refrain from eating for at least one hour prior to the study. Upon preparation, the patient is positioned in a prone posture. A small amount of oil or herbal juice is placed in a nasal bud, which is then gently administered into the nasal passage. The oil is allowed to remain in contact with the nasal mucosa for a few seconds, ensuring optimal absorption. Afterward, the bud is swiftly removed. Following the instillation, heat therapy is applied, and specific varmam points are stimulated to enhance the therapeutic effects. The procedure is completed by encouraging the patient to relax, ensuring a period of rest to enhance the effectiveness of the treatment.

CASE HISTORY:

This case series included participants who visited the Nanju Maruthuvam Department OPD of NIS, Tambaram, with primary complaints of sneezing, rhinitis, nasal congestion, headache and heaviness of head. Cases that were evaluated initially including the Naadi, history, physical examination, and grading based on the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT). Based on the Naadi observed during the physical exam, patients were then prescribed nasiyam oil. Demographic data were collected including age, sex, and personal and medical history with duration since the onset of the condition. Pre - Treatment and post-treatment were assessed by the SNOT Score.

All the demographic data including age, gender, occupation, affected side, duration, and vital signs of all the patients are described in Table 1

CASE 1:

A 27-year-old male working as an IT Professional came with complaints of headache on and off which relieves on vomiting, sneezing for 7 years. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 2:

A 22-year-old female being a homemaker came with the complaints of sneezing cold with rhinitis, cough with expectoration and headache for 3 months. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 3:

A 46 year old female being a clerk came with the complaints of sneezing, cold, cough with expectoration, heaviness of head, pain over the orbital cavity, pain in face, ear pain, post nasal drip since 1 month. The patient has nasal septal deviation since childhood. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 4:

A 23 years old male being an IT professional came with the complaints of cold, cough, sleeplessness, tiredness, rhinitis, head ache and vomiting head ache relieved on vomiting. The patient had an MRI stating gliosis in the brain. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 5:

A 27 year old female being a student came with the complaints of sneezing, cold, cough with expectoration, headache, ear pain, post nasal drip on and off since 2 years. The patient has nasal septal deviation since childhood. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 6:

A 66 year old male being a retired mine worker came with the complaints of cold, cough with expectoration, headache, post nasal drip, snoring on and off since 1 month. The patient has nasal polyp since childhood. The patient had Diabetes mellitus and Hypertention and was taking allopathy medicines for past 8 years.

CASE 7:

A 63 year old male came with the complaints of rhinitis, cold, headache, heaviness of head, cough, snoring, nasal congestion, tiredness for 1 month. The patient has Diabetes mellitus and Hyperlipidemia and was taking allopathy medicines since 10 years.

CASE 8:

A 62 year old male working as an interior designer came with the complaints of persistent morning sneezing, cold cough with expectoration, rhinitis, dypnea sleeplessness, since 1 month. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 9:

A 38 year old female being a home maker came with the complaints of sneezing, pain in the cheeks, head ache, nasal congestion on and off since 6 months frequently. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 10:

A 20 years old male being a student came with the complaints of nasal congestion on and off, sneezing, post nasal drip with thick yellow nasal discharge, ear pain head ache frequently since 3 years. The patient had no co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 11:

A 46/M came with the complaints of cold, cough, tearing of eye, facial pain, pain in orbital region, ear pain, tinnitus, running nose nasal congestion, sneezing, since 7 years on exposure to slight climatic changes and on waking up early. The patient had no comorbidity.

CASE 12:

A 22 year old female working in auditing office came with the complaints of pain in face with swelling over the face, ear pain, head ache, nasal congestion, running nose, cough with expectoration, cold sneezing persist early in the morning, itching over the nose since 1 year on and off frequently.

CASE 13:

A 56 years old female being a nurse came with the complaints of post nasal drip, cold, headache, cough with expectoration, pain in cheeks, ear pain running nose and sneezing since 3 months.

CASE 14:

A 25 year old female working as a teacher came with the complaints of headache, pain in face, cheeks and scalp, running nose, nasal congestion, sneezing on exposure to dust, itching of nose on and off frequently. The patient had hypothyroidism since 2 years and undergoing allopathy medicine. The patient had no any other co-morbidities or other relevant past history.

CASE 15:

A 33 year old female working in the rice mill came with the complaints of sneezing, headache, cold, rhinitis, post nasal drip, facial pain, ear pain, fullness of ear, dyspnea, chest congestion since 2 years.

**TABLE – 1 DEMOGRAPHIC DATA ON PATIENTS ENROLLED IN THE
STUDY**

Case series	Age/Sex	Occupation	Heart rate	Pulse rate	BP
Case 1	27/M	IT	83	83	130/70 mmHg
Case 2	22/F	Home maker	74	74	130/90 mmHg
Case 3	46/F	Clerk	74	74	130/90 mmHg
Case 4	23/M	IT	72	72	120/80 mmHg
Case 5	27/F	Student	72	72	110/70 mmHg
Case 6	66/M	Retired mine worker	74	74	130/80 mmHg
Case 7	60/M	Driver	74	78	130/90 mmHg
Case 8	62/M	Interior designer	96	80	130/80 mmHg
Case 9	38/F	Home maker	82	86	140/80 mmHg
Case 10	65/M	Security	88	84	120/80 mmHg
Case 11	46/M	Driver	72	70	110/80 mmHg
Case 12	22/F	Intern at Auditing Office	70	74	120/80 mmHg
Case 13	56/F	Nurse	86	90	130/80 mmHg
Case 14	25/F	Teacher	76	74	120/80 mmHg
Case 15	33/F	Rice Mill Worker	88	78	120/80 mmHg

TABLE – 2 PRE- AND POST- TREATMENT ASSESSMENT USING SNOT SCORE

Assessment	Pre-treatment (0th day)	Post-treatment (3rd day)
Case 1	34	0
Case 2	32	12
Case 3	45	18
Case 4	55	23
Case 5	34	8
Case 6	37	15
Case 7	23	7
Case 8	45	27
Case 9	14	4
Case 10	36	15
Case 11	36	9
Case 12	50	21
Case 13	37	12
Case 14	34	20
Case 15	35	14

Diagnostic assessment:

The prognosis was assessed by using Sino-Nasal Outcome Test 22 (SNOT) [10].

Treatment:

After observing all the signs and symptoms, the nasiyam therapy was done with Chukku thailam for 3 consequent days [11].

Outcome Measure:

The SNOT score allows patients to identify the items (maximum of 5 items) that are most important to them and which they hope will improve the most with therapy. A separate SNOT Score can be calculated as the sum of the items identified as important. The scores of each question range from 0 to 5, according to the severity of the symptom, with 5 being the worst. The score of the test is the sum of the question scores. Higher scores represent a lower health related-quality of life. In addition, patients identify the five items that affect them the most. Typically, the impact of treatment is assessed with the SNOT Absolute Change Score. Sino Nasal Outcome Test is used in this study to measure the prognosis of before and after treatment in sinusitis. The timeline of the clinical findings is depicted in Table 3 and Table 4 [10, 12].

Additionally, participants were asked to fill out an adverse event form if necessary. Participants were also asked to give their overall impressions about the Nasiyam therapy at the end of their study.

DISCUSSION:

Modern clinical guidelines recommend large-volume saline irrigation and intranasal corticosteroids as first-line therapies for chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) [11]. These treatments primarily reduce mucosal inflammation and improve sinus drainage. However, corticosteroids are associated with side effects such as mucosal dryness, epistaxis, and local irritation [12]. In

contrast, Nasiyam therapy using lipid-rich herbal oils like Chukku Thailam acts by lubricating and decongesting the nasal passages rather than chemically suppressing inflammation. This mechanical and moisturizing action aligns with traditional Siddha theories and may explain the rapid symptom relief observed in this case series. Pharmacologically, Chukku Thailam, based on *Zingiber officinale* (dried ginger) in sesame oil, leverages ginger's anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties [13]. Emerging evidence suggests that Nasiyam may also exert immunomodulatory effects, potentially rebalancing local immunity disturbed by Kapha disorders as per Siddha medicine [9].

The case series provides the potential efficacy of Nasiyam therapy; specifically using Chukku Thailam, for managing symptoms associated with sinusitis and related upper respiratory conditions. Chukku Thailam is an oil-based formulation commonly used for nasiyam therapy [14, 15]. The advantage of its lipid-soluble nature lies in its ability to be effectively absorbed through the mucous membranes when administered intranasally [16]. The nasal mucosa is rich in blood vessels with larger surface area (180cm²), which facilitates rapid absorption into the bloodstream [17]. Because Chukku Thailam is oil-based, it can bypass the typical barriers to absorption found in water-soluble substances. Lipid-soluble compounds have an affinity for the lipid layers in the cellular membranes, allowing them to permeate the mucosal lining more easily and efficiently [18]. Once absorbed through the nasal passage, the active compounds in Chukku Thailam are rapidly delivered into the systemic circulation, leading to a faster onset of action compared to other administration routes. When drugs are administered via powder inhalation, they can directly stimulate brain regions such as the limbic system and hypothalamus, offering a pathway for targeted neurological effects [19]. Thus, the lipid-soluble properties of Chukku

Thailam significantly enhance its bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness when used intranasally.

The treatment seems to be effective in reducing symptoms related to sinus and head diseases, as demonstrated by the considerable drop in SNOT scores for all participants. Participant 1, 5, 7, and 11 showed substantial improvement, with their scores nearly reaching zero or significantly lower values, indicating almost complete relief of symptoms. Most other cases experienced moderate improvement, showing a positive decrease in symptoms. The results of this study show promise in addressing common symptoms such as rhinitis and nasal congestion. The individual comparison between pre-test and post-test scores shows a consistent reduction across all 22 symptoms in SNOT. The Score differences ranged from 7 to 22 points, with most participants showing a reduction between 11 and 18 points. Through the pre- and post-treatment assessments using the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT), Nasiyam appears to have had a positive impact on patient health-related quality of life and symptom severity. In the presented case series, most patients demonstrated a reduction in symptoms over the three-day treatment period. Using the SNOT allowed for quantifiable tracking of symptom progression, helping validate the effects of Nasiyam with Chukku Thailam. The results showed no recurrence, indicating the lasting impact of the treatment. Furthermore, to ensure sustained benefits, patients continued to receive weekly Nasiyam administration for one month after the initial treatment.

This case series included a limited number of participants, which may restrict the generalizability of the results. A larger, randomized control study could better establish the efficacy and safety profile of Nasiyam for sinusitis. Also, future studies might consider comparing Nasiyam with other sinusitis treatments, including allopathic options, to better

understand its relative efficacy. Also, studies may be conducted to evaluate the efficacy of nasiyam in the treatment of neurological and ENT related diseases.

CONCLUSION:

The findings from this study clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of Nasiyam as a therapeutic intervention for managing sinusitis and chronic rhinitis. This traditional treatment has shown promising results in providing substantial symptomatic relief, improving the quality of life, and preventing the recurrence of these conditions. Its potential to offer a holistic approach to upper respiratory health makes it a valuable addition to integrative medical practices.

Additionally, investigations into its long-term benefits, potential side effects, and comparative efficacy with modern therapeutic options could solidify its role in managing sinusitis, chronic rhinitis and other head and neck related disorders. Such evidence-based studies could pave the way for Nasiyam to be recognized and adopted as a mainstream therapeutic approach for respiratory disorders.

Study Limitations:

The study was limited by a small sample size of 15 participants, restricting its statistical power and generalizability. The absence of a control group hindered the comparative analysis with standard treatments. The reliance on subjective SNOT scores without objective assessments like imaging or nasal endoscopy may introduce bias. The adverse events were self-reported, lacking a structured monitoring protocol, potentially underreporting safety concerns.

Future recommendations:

Future studies should include larger, multi-center RCTs with extended follow-up to assess long-term efficacy, safety, and recurrence rates while incorporating objective measures like imaging and biomarkers. Comparative analysis with standard treatments, dosage optimization, and mechanistic studies of Chukku Thailam are recommended, along with evaluating broader applications in ENT and neurological conditions and implementing structured safety monitoring.

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Patient perspectives:

The patients expressed great satisfaction with the treatment, reporting significant relief in headache, rhinitis, and enhanced quality of life. They were particularly impressed with the effectiveness of the Nasiyam therapy in alleviating their symptoms and preventing sinusitis recurrence.

Informed consent:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patients. The patients had given their consent for their images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patients understood that their names and initials would not be published, and due efforts would be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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